

Integrity Validation of Evidence

- User Manual -

Project Title:	MEDINA - Security Framework to achieve a continuous audit-based certification in compliance with the EU-wide cloud security certification scheme
Project Number:	952633
Editor:	Cristina Regueiro (Fundación TECNALIA Research and Innovation)
Version:	v1.0
Date:	31.07.2023
Distribution level:	PU

Table of contents

1. Introduction	4
1.1. User Roles and Permissions	4
2. User Manual	5
2.1. Toolbar	5
2.2. List of Evidence	5
2.3. Evidence	6
2.4. List of Assessment Results	7
2.5. Assessment Result	8
3. Blockchain viewer client	11
4. Delivery and usage	13
4.1. Licensing information	13
4.2. More information	13

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. MEDINA EVIDENCE TRUSTWORTHINESS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM TOOLBAR.....	5
FIGURE 2. LIST OF EVIDENCE FILTERING OPTIONS.....	5
FIGURE 3. LIST OF EVIDENCE VALIDATION RESULT.....	6
FIGURE 4. EVIDENCE INPUT	6
FIGURE 5. EVIDENCE CORRECT RESULT.....	7
FIGURE 6. EVIDENCE INCORRECT RESULT.....	7
FIGURE 7. LIST OF ASSESSMENT RESULTS FILTERING OPTIONS.....	8
FIGURE 8. LIST OF ASSESSMENT RESULTS VALIDATION RESULT.....	8
FIGURE 9. ASSESSMENT RESULT INPUT.....	9
FIGURE 10. ASSESSMENT RESULT CORRECT RESULT	9
FIGURE 11. ASSESSMENT RESULT INCORRECT RESULT	10
FIGURE 12. BLOCKCHAIN VIEWER CLIENT DASHBOARD	12

1. Introduction

The functionality of Integrity Validation of Evidence in MEDINA is provided by the Blockchain based *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*, which provides a secure mechanism to maintain an audit trail of evidence and assessment results. The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is implemented in **Smart Contracts** backed by a common **Blockchain network** for all the MEDINA framework instances, providing the following **functionalities**:

- Includes the logic for all *Orchestrator*¹ instances in MEDINA to **provide the required information to be audited** (about evidence and assessment results). For this purpose, an API is exposed by the Blockchain client.
- Provides **secure long-term information recording**, thanks to the inherent advantages of Blockchain (integrity, decentralization, authenticity...):
 - It provides a record of information on a verifiable way (**verification**).
 - It provides a record of information on a permanent way (**traceability**).
 - It guarantees resistance to modification of stored data (**integrity**).
- Includes the logic for external users to **access MEDINA's audited information** (about evidence and assessment results) **in a graphical and user-friendly way** through a kibana-based dashboard.
- Includes the logic for **automatic verification of hashes** from currently recorded information on the Orchestrator with hashes recorded on the Blockchain.

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* is managed by Keycloak². All authenticated users, regardless their roles, can perform “read” actions from the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* UIs (“write” actions are not allowed through UI). The non-authenticated customer role has no access to any of the UIs.

The table below details which actions are allowed for each of the defined roles:

Roles	Allowed Actions
IT Security Governance	Read information
Security Analyst	Read information
Domain Governance	Read information
Product and Service Owner	Read information
Product (Security) Engineer	Read information
Chief Information Security Office (CISO)	Read information
Customer	None
Auditor	Read information

¹ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D3.6 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225>

² <https://www.keycloak.org>

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* includes a toolbar (see Figure 1), always accessible in the upper area, with all the options that are available in the tool:

Figure 1. MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System toolbar

The different menu options, which are described in the following sections, are as follows:

- **List of Evidence:** Provides access to the automatic verification status of the complete list of recorded evidence in the *Orchestrator* comparing their current values with the ones previously recorded on the Blockchain.
- **Evidence:** Provides access to the automatic verification status of a specific piece of evidence defined by its ID.
- **List of Assessment Results:** Provides access to the automatic verification status of the complete list of recorded assessment results in the *Orchestrator* comparing their current values with the ones previously recorded on the Blockchain.
- **Assessment Result:** Provides access to the automatic verification status of a specific assessment result by its ID.
- **Help:** Provides access to the user manual.

2.2. List of Evidence

The *List of Evidence* view is useful to automatically obtain the overall evidence integrity status. Figure 2 shows the available optional filtering options to be applied to the list of evidence to be validated: cloud service ID or tool ID can be provided.

Figure 2. List of Evidence filtering options

Once the filtering options have been completed as needed, the user must click on the *Submit* button. As a result, the complete list of recorded evidence on the *Orchestrator* (after filtering data) is displayed, as shown in Figure 3. For each recorded evidence, the “ID” and the “Integrity check” status is shown. The integrity status is automatically obtained; for each piece of evidence, it can be:

- Correct (“green tick”) if the automatically calculated hash of the piece of evidence recorded on the *Orchestrator* matches the hash value previously recorded on the Blockchain.

- Incorrect (“red cross”) if the automatically calculated hash of the piece of evidence recorded on the *Orchestrator* does not match the hash value previously recorded on the Blockchain.

Evidence ID	Integrity Check
79f6d84d-1686-4605-b7d5-f1c789b74b6e	✓
176ab185-0a9f-434d-85df-3c0f2cd1a7d8	✓
ddc76419-0fbd-4daa-b9f5-a0bd5113b82c	✗
61da7d64-1143-460a-ba75-38f695641212	✓
156f5a1b-a006-4cc9-87c2-6eb72c2e1e5f	✓
19a9f11e-3c14-4973-b788-8bf9ff930699	✓
b199daba-3645-4a69-a831-593c840d7101	✓
71fab566-37ec-49af-812b-038caa893925	✓
28eab3c5-5db2-4bb2-8d14-a894df145a50	✓
7925efef-cb32-49fe-ae07-32912e1ab8bf	✓
432a6c71-1dcf-4036-bd10-39d7b87e1c0e	✓
6b7ff38e-3c34-49ac-a3df-de564d10ae46	✓
137db061-254f-4f87-a816-f26306a64b97	✓
d20e0ae0-fc9b-4ec4-81ae-13c8b77d1a5e	✓

Figure 3. List of Evidence validation result

2.3. Evidence

The *Evidence* view allows the automatic comparison of a piece of evidence value with the value recorded on the Blockchain. This option is especially useful when an incorrect integrity check has been obtained in the “List of Evidence” overall evidence integrity check (see Figure 3). Figure 4 shows the form to enter the required piece of evidence ID to be validated.

MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness System

Please, provide the **Evidence ID** to be validated:

Evidence ID:

Figure 4. Evidence input

Once the evidence ID has been provided, the user must click on the *Submit* button. As a result, the following information is displayed for the specific evidence:

- **Evidence ID:** identifier of the piece of evidence.
- **Orchestrator Hash:** automatically obtained for the evidence currently recorded on the *Orchestrator*. If information related to the specific evidence ID is not available in the *Orchestrator* for any reason, “Not found” will be displayed.
- **Blockchain Hash:** automatically obtained from the Blockchain. If information related to the specific evidence ID is not available in the Blockchain for any reason, “Not found” will be displayed.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show examples of correct and incorrect evidence integrity checks, respectively.

Figure 5. Evidence correct result

Figure 6. Evidence incorrect result

2.4. List of Assessment Results

The *List of Assessment Results* view is useful to automatically obtain the overall integrity status of the assessment results. Figure 7 shows the available optional filtering options to be applied to the list of assessment results to be validated: cloud service ID or metric ID can be provided. Additionally, it is also possible to filter out only compliant results by clicking on the *Only Compliant results* checkbox.

Once the filtering options have been completed as needed, the user must click on the *Submit* button. As a result, the complete list of recorded assessment results on the *Orchestrator* (after filtering data) is displayed, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7. List of Assessment Results filtering options

The provided results are the same as for evidence: for each recorded assessment result, the “ID” and the “Integrity check” status is shown. The integrity status is automatically obtained; for each assessment result, it can be:

- Correct (“green tick”) if the automatically calculated hash of the assessment result recorded on the *Orchestrator* matches the hash value previously recorded on the Blockchain.
- Incorrect (“red cross”) if the automatically calculated hash of the assessment result recorded on the *Orchestrator* does not match the hash value previously recorded on the Blockchain.

The screenshot shows the 'MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness System' interface displaying a table of assessment results. The table has two columns: 'Assessment Result ID' and 'Integrity Check'. The message above the table reads: 'This is the current integrity check status of the MEDINA assessment results'. All entries in the table show a green checkmark in the 'Integrity Check' column, indicating that all assessment results passed the integrity check.

Assessment Result ID	Integrity Check
d98fd62-a627-4437-afb7-e1101ad32ade	✓
70a472b0-0ec9-42d7-9be9-93696af85099	✓
99e2c349-8874-4fc8-baac-0753b5750916	✓
f2926efc-2f8f-4d2c-93ca-7c6cfeb1b5fa	✓
94f2c9f3-9c21-4a74-a98d-542d555c7f53	✓
8bd56099-fd91-4c36-aac4-b2b6e9a2cbb6	✓
7922be00-3bed-44d8-8d83-63ae661d401a	✓
90eeaf80-2477-41ba-87e4-0983f7e191a0	✓
81a83e59-5d25-46e6-9cf8-e7b7726962fb	✓
3b57875d-1ad0-4e5e-94bd-b0665360d4a8	✓
e9c2de09-745c-481e-ad62-38fbc12beb88	✓
b4cde218-dfc0-482e-be31-9b2d1cb15f8e	✓

Figure 8. List of Assessment Results validation result

2.5. Assessment Result

The *Assessment Result* view allows the automatic comparison of an assessment result value with the value recorded on the Blockchain. This option is especially useful when an incorrect integrity check has been obtained in the “List of Assessment Result” overall assessment results integrity check (see Figure 8). Figure 9 shows the form to enter the assessment result ID to be validated.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar with links: List of Evidence, Evidence, List of Assessment Results, Assessment Result, and Help. Below the navigation bar, the page title is "MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness System". The main content area contains the text "Please, provide the Assessment Result ID to be validated:" followed by an input field labeled "Assessment Result ID:". Below the input field is a teal "Submit" button.

Figure 9. Assessment Result input

Once the assessment result ID has been provided, the user must click on the *Submit* button. As a result, the same information as for the evidence is shown:

- **Assessment Result ID:** identifier of the assessment result.
- **Orchestrator Hash:** automatically obtained for the assessment result currently recorded on the *Orchestrator*. If information related to the specific assessment result ID is not available in the *Orchestrator* for any reason, “Not found” will be shown.
- **Blockchain Hash:** automatically obtained from the Blockchain. If information related to the specific assessment result ID is not available in the Blockchain for any reason, “Not found” will be shown.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show examples of correct and incorrect assessment result integrity checks, respectively.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar with links: List of Evidence, Evidence, List of Assessment Results, Assessment Result, and Help. Below the navigation bar, the page title is "MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness System". The main content area contains the text "These are the MEDINA assessment result hashes:" followed by a table:

Assessment Result ID	d98fdf62-a627-4437-afb7-e1101ad32ade
Orchestrator Hash	02372a3e8ed75ba0cdbd7e8fa79e1f232b8a1a0da0d451db38ece22a80e9adb5
Blockchain Hash	02372a3e8ed75ba0cdbd7e8fa79e1f232b8a1a0da0d451db38ece22a80e9adb5

Below the table is a large teal checkmark icon and a teal "Return" button.

Figure 10. Assessment Result correct result

Figure 11. Assessment Result incorrect result

3. Blockchain viewer client

The *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* also exposes a Kibana-based graphical interface available at: <https://kibana.medina.bclab.dev/> [internal use only - authentication is required] for manual graphical access to the information recorded on the Blockchain.

Figure 12 shows the main dashboard for each *Orchestrator* instance. Here, the complete list of registered evidence (evidence hashes) and assessment results (assessment result hashes) is shown. This information is useful for manual verifications. Additionally, a summary of the total number of registered evidence and assessment results for the specific *Orchestrator* instance is shown.

For evidence, the following information is shown:

- Evidence ID
- Evidence Hash
- Resource
- Evidence Collector
- CSP
- *Orchestrator* timestamp (when evidence was received in the *Orchestrator*).
- Blockchain timestamp (when evidence was recorded on the Blockchain).

For assessment results, the following information is shown:

- Assessment Result ID
- Assessment Result Hash
- Metric
- Associated evidence
- *Orchestrator* timestamp (when assessment result was received in the *Orchestrator*).
- Blockchain timestamp (when assessment result was recorded on the Blockchain).

Finally different filters have been included for improving the usability of the system: filter by id, hash or associated metadata on the evidence and assessment results.

MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System

Number of pieces of evidence

3,458

Number of assessment results

1,608

Evidences

Look for a specific...

Apply changes Cancel changes Clear form

Evidence Id	Evidence Hash	Resource	Evidence Collector	CSP	Orchestrator timestamp	Blockchain timestamp per day
18de7d36-e89f-4347-8d44-245c76f9da70	ca83f377588407af09f1d19a5742d8df9cb603a3ef76f343...	Resource for MEDINA workflow tests	Fabasoft Cloud Service Assessment Tool	N/A	1686730429073910450	2023-06-14
105f600a-30e3-42f0-9eb8-937c9d08c6eb	44fc32f500c7912e64713f4e14acd2c9f14d1c3785184f0...	Resource for MEDINA workflow tests	Fabasoft Cloud Service Assessment Tool	N/A	1686730414562766220	2023-06-14
159c0216-149f-4794-9e43-0b8d5deef790	443c50c16811aca5a64829d193e8a25d393b4a04f20e77...	Resource for MEDINA workflow tests	Fabasoft Cloud Service Assessment Tool	N/A	1686730412521761029	2023-06-14
1af71cec-d9d2-4f03-a484-e55e98693033	d6a63dc34dfb89b61bc6d5d3d80c9283efaa9d48d074e8...	Resource for MEDINA workflow tests	Fabasoft Cloud Service Assessment Tool	N/A	1686730409455936503	2023-06-14
0beaf068-addr-4fcb-933a-997b6fd3568c	8bd81c38c35b2658f9cca79cfe2097c62a9060e05b5...	Resource for MEDINA workflow tests	Fabasoft Cloud Service Assessment Tool	N/A	1686730394046231131	2023-06-14
189de95b-709e-4ce6-9d72-2f84dec3086	809ab019b0ec183cc1a55514542d0ceded9c83aabd00...	Resource for MEDINA workflow tests	Fabasoft Cloud Service Assessment Tool	N/A	168673038868654537	2023-06-14

Assessment Results

Look for a specific...

Apply changes Cancel changes Clear form

Figure 12. Blockchain viewer client dashboard

4. Delivery and usage

4.1. Licensing information

This component is offered under Proprietary License. Copyright by TECNALIA.

4.2. More information

Interested readers can find more information about the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System* at this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927220> “D3.3 Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence - v3”.

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables and blog posts related to the *MEDINA Evidence Trustworthiness Management System*.